

The Effect of Cognitive Behavior Therapy in Adolescents with Mythomania Disorder in Ehime Mbano Local Government of Imo State

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to explore the effect of cognitive behavior therapy in adolescents with Mythomania disorder in Ehime Mbano Local Government of Imo State. Mythomania refers to a compulsive tendency to lie and deceive others. It is not simply a choice to deceive, but rather a psychological condition that drives individuals to fabricate stories, exaggerate facts, or falsify information. Compulsive lying can become a habitual behavior for those with mythomania. A literature search was conducted using the CINAHL and MEDLINE databases. The database search occurred during the month of January 2024. This article comprehensively summarizes the theoretical basis of CBT in improving Mythomania disorder, its application in managing symptoms and improving social function, as well as research progress in this field. There are still inconsistencies in the research results on CBT, but overall, psychological intervention combined with drug treatment is more effective than conventional treatment alone. If social function training can be added at the same time, it is believed that it will have better effects on clinical treatment and can maintain long-lasting effectiveness. Only in this way can adolescents truly understand and recognize the disease, improve treatment compliance, and ultimately achieve the goal of improving the disorder and have quality of life. Therapists or psychologists use CBT for adolescents to help them become aware of irrational or negative thinking so they can see situations clearly, process them, and respond to them in healthy ways. CBT intervention for adolescents can be a powerful part of an integrated treatment plan for adolescent mental health disorders.

Key Words: Cognitive, Behavior, Therapy, Adolescents, Mythomania, Disorder, Ehime Mbano

INTRODUCTION

Pathological lying usually starts when a person is in their adolescents. They often continue the pattern for years. This behavior can be part of a personality disorder such as antisocial, narcissistic, and histrionic. A lie is changing the truth deliberately to reach an objective. This is frequently encountered in childhood period, as much adult individuals could sometimes use innocent lies throughout their lives. This condition that could be encountered often with children, could also be observed among healthy adults in the form of innocent lies. Mythomania, known as lying pathologically, is an individual lying about almost anything in various environments and believing in these lies. This article aims to analyze within the context of literature, the clinical findings about adolescents suffering from mythomania,

Mythomania is a psychological condition characterised by an uncontrollable urge to lie, fabricate stories, and present false information as truth. It goes beyond occasional white lies or exaggerations. Individuals with mythomania often create elaborate narratives, with lies becoming a central part of their identity and interpersonal interactions. They may lie about their achievements, experiences, and relationships or invent fictitious events. The motives behind mythomania can vary, including a desire for attention, validation, or a defense mechanism to cover up insecurities or past trauma. Living with mythomania can have profound consequences for adolescents and their relationships. Over time, the lies may strain trust, leading to strained friendships, broken partnerships, and damaged reputations. Adolescents with mythomania often experience a constant fear of being exposed, which can lead to heightened anxiety, stress, and a sense of isolation. The cycle of lying becomes a source of guilt and shame, perpetuating a negative self-perception and reinforcing the need to continue fabricating stories.

Cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) is a first-line psychotherapeutic treatment that has been proven effective in treating a variety of psychiatric disorders such as major depressive disorder (MDD), anxiety disorder (AD), and obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) (Butler et al., 2006; Beck and Dozois, 2011; Hofmann et al., 2012; McMMain et al., 2015). This psychotherapy, pioneered by Ellis (1962) and Beck (1970), focuses on identifying maladaptive cognitions and modifying behavioral patterns to alleviate clinical symptoms and improve function (Beck and Dozois, 2011; Hofmann et al., 2012). Moreover, CBT may promote change in conflict and inflexible appraisals of emotional, cognitive, physiological, and social states by reducing avoidance in experience and behavior (McMMain et al., 2015).

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Framework

Mythomania, as mentioned, is an unhealthy condition that becomes chronic over time and can lead the adolescents building their life on great fiction and lies. Although there are certain common characteristics and symptoms among people who lie, it should be remembered that this is a unique and complex process for each individual. Mythomania is often caused by another mental health

problem, antisocial personality disorder, narcissistic personality disorder, impulse control disorder, etc. (Vuper, Philippi, & Bruce, 2021).

Therefore, the adolescent's history, general mental health status, and the underlying causes of the behavior should be thoroughly investigated. At this stage, especially in cases accompanied by a personality disorder, psychological support as well as treatment are of critical importance. (Asunción, Silva, 2019).

Mythomania is a psychological problem in which people feel the need to lie, often chronically and without any purpose or benefit. Lying behavior can start with a simple, daily lie and become chronic over time and turn into mythomania. Adolescents with this disorder are called mythomaniacs. There are certain reasons why mythomaniacs are differentiated from people who exhibit daily lying behavior and why it is referred to as a disorder. The most important reason for this is that the lies told by people with mythomania occur impulsively in all areas of life, and the lies told do not serve any purpose (getting what you want, avoiding a negative situation, showing kindness, protecting someone else, etc.). On the other hand, it is thought that mythomaniacs believe the lies they tell to a great extent themselves. These people can continue their lying behavior without experiencing any serious problems in their daily lives. (Beck, Dozois, 2024).

Although there is limited scientific literature on who may be more prone to mythomania and the causes of mythomania due to the lack of research on mythomania, various childhood experiences and low self-esteem may be considered to be effective in the development of mythomania. The first step in rebuilding a relationship after mythomania is to be honest and open about the condition. The person with mythomania should be willing to acknowledge the harm that their lies have caused and take responsibility for their actions. They should also be willing to seek help and commit to changing their behaviour. (Bomyea, Ball, Simmons & Campbell-Sills, 2020).

The next step is to work on rebuilding trust. This can be a slow and difficult process and may require the help of a therapist or counsellor. It is important for the person with mythomania to be consistent in their honesty and to follow through on their commitments. They should also be willing to listen to their partner's feelings and needs and work to meet them in a genuine way. In addition to rebuilding trust, it may also be necessary to work on other aspects of the relationship. (Reinecke, Thilo, Croft, & Harmer, 2023). This may involve improving communication skills, practicing empathy, and developing a stronger emotional connection. Couples therapy can be a helpful tool for addressing these issues and creating a plan for moving forward. Ultimately, rebuilding a relationship after mythomania requires patience, commitment, and a willingness to work through the challenges. It is important for both partners to be supportive of each other and to communicate openly and honestly. With the right treatment and a strong commitment to change, it is possible to overcome the impact of mythomania on a relationship and rebuild a strong and healthy connection based on trust and honesty. (Broyd, Demanuele, Debener & James, 2024).

Symptoms of Mythomania

Consistent pattern of lying, elaborate storytelling, inconsistencies in narratives, lack of guilt or remorse, impulsive lying, fantastical claims, difficulty maintaining relationships, emotional instability, unnecessary complication, low self-esteem and insecurity. When we look at the causes of mythomania, some common personality traits have been observed in individuals who lie pathologically. It has been observed that mythomaniacs are generally people with low self-esteem and intense insecurity. These two conditions are generally thought to be important factors in the development and continuation of mythomania. (Vuper, Philippi & Bruce, 2021).

Childhood Experiences

It is thought that certain experiences in a person's childhood history and situations that have a direct impact on their mental and physical health may be equally influential in the development of mythomania. Possible past experiences for people who develop lying disorders can be as follows: Traumatic events experienced or witnessed as a child. Sexual, physical, or emotional abuse. Consistently witnessing their parents lie (role model learning). Having a co-existing personality disorder (borderline personality disorder, antisocial personality disorder, impulse control problems, etc.). Intense need for appreciation, approval, and attention and head traumas. (McMain, Newman. Segal, Derubeis, 2023). Pathological lying behavior is a disorder that is often rooted in childhood experiences and usually begins to manifest itself in adolescence (often between 15 and 16 years of age). Left untreated, it can persist into adulthood. In addition to childhood experiences, there are current views that mythomania can develop as a result of a traumatic head injury and changes in the brain. (Bruijn, Schoemaker, & Janssen, 2022).

Lying Disorder and Psychotherapy Process

During the therapy process, it is important for the person with lying disorder to be clearly aware of his or her situation, to be conscious of his or her recurrent lying behavior, and to be motivated to continue the process. (Kircher .Arolt, Jansen, Reinhardt & Kellermann et al. 2023). It is known that people with lying disorders often do not seek any support because they believe the lies they tell and therefore are not aware of their condition. For this reason, when mythomania is detected in people who come to therapy for the support of family members or for another mental health problem, the person should first be informed about the existing situation in a concise, clear, and non-judgmental manner. As in other areas of one's life, it is possible to lie to one's therapist during the therapy process. It is important for the therapist to be aware that the client may also lie to him or her and to emphasize in a gentle and clear way that this may negatively affect the course of the therapy process. This safe, open, and collaborative relationship between the therapist and the client can positively affect the client's insecurity in this aspect alone. (Monosov, Haber, & Leuthardt, Jezzini, 2020).

Treatment for Adolescents who lie compulsively

To determine whether your teen's lying is connected to any one of these mental health disorders, the best choice is to seek a clinical evaluation by a mental health professional sooner, rather than later. Depending on the outcome of the evaluation, your teen may require treatment at a residential treatment facility or outpatient treatment center for adolescents. Compulsive or pathological lying can cause numerous problems in an adolescent's life, including but not limited to strained

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relationships with family and friends, problems at school, and even legal consequences. Therapists often recommend professional intervention for teens who lie pathologically or compulsively. If there's a mental health disorder involved, mental health professionals almost always advocate treatment and support as soon as possible when an individual who needs treatment for a mental health disorder waits to receive that treatment, the healing and recovery process becomes more challenging. (La Buissonniere-Ariza, Goodman, et al. 2021).

If you spend most of your day-to-day life with someone who is a mythomaniac, it is clear that constant exposure to lying behavior can be challenging. Experts therefore offer suggestions to make life more comfortable for people who have a lying disorder in close proximity: Recognize that the other person has a significant health problem and remind yourself of this at intervals. Set healthy boundaries in the relationship with the person with mythomania and remind them of these boundaries from time to time. Recognize lying behavior that arises from insecurity and the need to prove oneself, and in a non-critical, gentle, and compassionate manner, convey the message that the relationship between you does not need it. When lying behavior is detected, share clearly how it makes you feel using I language (e.g., "When you lie, I feel sad and helpless."). Remind yourself that it is quite natural and understandable to feel angry and helpless at times in the face of a mythomaniac. Calmly communicate the negative emotions you feel towards the other person. Get information about mythomania from reliable and scientific sources and encourage the person to seek psychological support accordingly. (Hauer, Mineka, Voss, & Paller, 2020).

Exploring the Motivations behind Adolescent Compulsive Lying

Understanding the motivations behind compulsive lying in adolescents can provide valuable insights into their behavior and help parents, educators, and healthcare professionals address the underlying causes. While each individual's motivations may vary, several common factors contribute to this behavior. Bockting, (Van Den., et al. 2024). This section explores three key motivations behind adolescent compulsive lying: the desire for attention and acceptance, fear of consequences or judgment, and coping mechanisms and emotional regulation. One of the primary motivations behind compulsive lying in adolescents is the desire for attention and acceptance. Adolescence is a time of significant social development, and teens may resort to lying as a means of fitting in or gaining approval from their peers. By fabricating stories or exaggerating the truth, they hope to capture the attention and admiration of others. It is important for parents and guardians to create an environment where adolescents feel valued and accepted for who they are. Encouraging open and honest communication, providing positive reinforcement, and fostering a supportive social network can help mitigate the need for teens to resort to lying for attention or acceptance. (Fonzo, Simmons, & Paulus, 2022).

Fear of Consequences or Judgment

Another motivation behind compulsive lying in teenagers is the fear of facing consequences or judgment. Teens may lie to avoid punishment, disappointment, or criticism from their parents, teachers, or authority. They may believe that telling the truth will result in negative consequences, leading them to fabricate stories or withhold information. To address this motivation, it is crucial for parents and guardians to create an environment based on trust and understanding. Establishing

open lines of communication and setting clear expectations with consequences that are fair and consistent can help alleviate the fear of negative repercussions. By fostering an atmosphere of trust, adolescents may feel more comfortable sharing their thoughts and experiences without resorting to compulsive lying. (Reinecke, Thilo, Croft, & Harmer, 2023).

Coping Mechanisms and Emotional Regulation

Compulsive lying can also serve as a coping mechanism for emotional difficulties or challenges that teenagers may face. Lying may provide a temporary escape from emotional distress, anxiety, or low self-esteem. By creating alternative narratives, teens may feel a sense of control or protection from their perceived vulnerabilities. To address this motivation, it is important for parents, educators, and healthcare professionals to support adolescents in developing healthy coping mechanisms and emotional regulation skills. Encouraging teens to express their emotions, providing them with appropriate outlets for stress, and teaching problem-solving strategies can help them navigate challenging situations without resorting to compulsive lying. Understanding the motivations behind teen compulsive lying is crucial for effectively addressing and supporting individuals who engage in this behavior. By recognizing the desire for attention and acceptance, fear of consequences or judgment, and the role of coping mechanisms and emotional regulation, parents and guardians can take proactive steps to promote open communication, establish trust, and provide the necessary support for teens to overcome compulsive lying habits. (Qian, Wang, Li, Gao, 2020).

Building Self-Esteem and Confidence

One effective way to address compulsive lying in adolescents is by focusing on building their self-esteem and confidence. Low self-esteem can often contribute to the need for attention or acceptance, which may lead to compulsive lying as a means of gaining validation. Encouraging positive self-talk, celebrating achievements, and providing opportunities for success can enhance a teen's self-perception and reduce the desire to lie for validation. (Xu W., Chen S., Xue W., et al. 2020).

Teaching Problem-Solving and Conflict Resolution Skills

Adolescents who struggle with compulsive lying may lack effective problem-solving and conflict resolution skills. Teaching these skills can empower them to navigate challenging situations without resorting to dishonesty. Encourage open discussions about conflicts, brainstorming potential solutions, and practicing effective communication techniques. By equipping them with these skills, they can learn to address issues transparently and honestly. (Reinhardt, & Kellermann 2023).

Encouraging Honesty and Accountability

Promoting honesty and accountability is crucial in helping adolescents overcome compulsive lying. Establish clear expectations regarding honesty and emphasize the importance of taking responsibility for one's actions. Create an environment where honesty is rewarded and understood

as a valuable trait. When a teenager does admit to lying, it is essential to address the behavior calmly and constructively, focusing on the importance of truthfulness. (Matsumoto, (Hamatani, & Shimizu. 2021). By employing these strategies, parents and guardians can support them in their journey towards overcoming compulsive lying. It is important to remember that each adolescent is unique, and progress may take time. If the lying behavior persists or worsens despite these interventions, seeking professional help from a therapist or counselor experienced in working with adolescents may provide additional guidance and support. (Rubin-Falcone, Weber, Delaparte, Doré et al. 2020).

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Butler, Chapman, Forman, & Beck, (2024), found out that a significant part of children and adolescents' hysterical symptoms are effects of emotional trauma. After the trauma they become very sensitive to the adults' reactions. Conversion disorder in adolescents debuts by the age of 12. Individuals affected are mostly girls (2/3 of the total number of cases. (Pyka. Kellermann, et al. 2023). According to Asunción e Silva (2019), compulsive lying in teenagers can stem from various underlying factors. One potential cause is low self-esteem, as teens may feel the need to fabricate stories or achievements to gain validation and acceptance from others. Additionally, teenagers dealing with mental health conditions such as borderline personality disorder or narcissistic personality disorder may exhibit compulsive lying as a symptom. (McMain Newman, Segal, Derubeis, 2023).

Bruijn, Schoemaker, & Janssen, (2022), using regression analysis and causality estimation test on data ranging from (2011 to 2021), examined the treatment of mythomania as often complex and multi-faceted. Treatment approaches vary and often include a combination of psychotherapy, pharmacotherapy, and cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT). (Karakamis et al., 2018). Psychotherapy can be used to explore the underlying motivations for the fabrications and to help the patient develop more adaptive coping strategies. Pharmacotherapy may also be used to address comorbid conditions such as depression or anxiety. (Bruijn et al., 2016). Finally, CBT can be helpful in addressing the cognitive distortions and maladaptive thinking patterns associated with the disorder. (Karakamis et al., 2018).

Álvarez-Pérez, & Rivero, (2021) examine how compulsive lying can have a significant impact on an adolescent's mental health. The constant need to fabricate and maintain false narratives can lead to increased anxiety, stress, and difficulty in developing genuine relationships. It can also contribute to a downward trajectory in a teen's emotional well-being, exacerbating existing mental health conditions or creating new challenges. Recognizing and addressing compulsive lying in teenagers is a collaborative effort. As parents, it is essential to approach the issue with empathy, open communication, and professional support. Engaging in dialogue and expressing concerns without judgment can create an environment where a teenager feels safe to open up. (Karakamis Stavarakaki, Gkontzis, & Mouratidis, 2023).

Zhou & Yingliang (2021), are of the view that to curb compulsive lying, it may be necessary to seek professional intervention. Counseling or therapy sessions can help teenagers explore the deeper reasons behind their lying behavior and develop healthier coping mechanisms.

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Additionally, involving other trusted individuals, such as school counselors or mental health professionals, can provide a comprehensive approach to support a teenager's journey. The result also shows that compulsive lying in teenagers is often a symptom of a larger mental health issue or underlying self-esteem issues. (Vuper, Philippi & Bruce 2021). By creating a healthy parent-teen relationship built on trust, understanding, and open dialogue, parents can positively impact their teenager's well-being. Seeking appropriate support, is essential in navigating this challenging territory and helping teenagers develop healthier patterns of communication and honesty. (Asunción, & Silva, 2019).

Goodman et al. (2021), found out that if parents are struggling to establish open communication and address issues of dishonesty, seeking professional help can be beneficial. Therapists and counselors specialize in supporting families and can provide guidance tailored to the specific needs of teenagers struggling with honesty. Their study found that for honesty and communication are vital components of a healthy parent-teen relationship. By modeling honesty, fostering a safe and non-judgmental environment, encouraging open dialogue, setting clear boundaries, and seeking professional help if needed, parents can create an environment that promotes honesty, trust, and strong communication skills in their teenagers. Understanding compulsive lying in teenagers is crucial for parents seeking to address and support their teens effectively, and there is some good news in the form of research that shows that teens tend to age out of lying to their parents during college years. (Rubin-Falcone, Weber, Kishon, Ochsner, Delaparte & Doré 2020).

Heuvel R. M., et al. (2024). Suggest that creating an environment of trust and non-judgment is essential for teenagers to feel comfortable expressing themselves truthfully. By actively listening without interrupting, offering empathy, and validating their feelings, parents can build strong lines of communication. It is important to resist the temptation to react with anger or punishment when confronted with uncomfortable truths, as this can deter teenagers from being honest in the future. Engaging in regular, meaningful conversations with teenagers can strengthen the parent-child relationship and encourage honesty. It is essential to ask open-ended questions that encourage reflection and self-expression. By actively listening and validating their perspectives, parents can promote communication that is free from fear of judgment. (Reinecke. Thilo, Croft, & Harmer 2023).

Beck & Dozois (2024). Found out that one of the primary reasons teenagers lie is to escape punishment. Fear of consequences often drives them to conceal their mistakes or misbehavior. As parents, it is crucial to create a safe and supportive environment where honesty is encouraged and consequences focus on learning and growth rather than punishment. Encourage open communication and assure your teen that you are there to help them navigate challenges. Adolescents often lie to project a certain image to their peers. The pressure to fit in and gain acceptance can lead them to exaggerate achievements or fabricate stories. Help your teen build a strong sense of self-worth based on their true strengths and values. Encourage them to develop genuine friendships based on mutual trust and respect rather than trying to impress others through dishonesty. (La Buissonniere-Ariza, Goodman, et al. 2021).

Low self-esteem can be a significant factor in teenage lying. Teens may lie to cover up their insecurities and present themselves in a more favorable light. Show unconditional love and support

to your teen, helping them develop a positive self-image. Encourage them to embrace their strengths and work on areas that need improvement, fostering a healthy sense of self-esteem. This might be hard for you to read, but sometimes adolescents lie to their parents out of fear of their parent's reaction. If you have reacted poorly to a teen, it could be a reason as to why they are reluctant to tell you the truth, and might be a reason for being dishonest. You might try acknowledging this in a conversation "I know the last time you told me X, I got very upset, and want assure you I am not going to react the same way". It is not going to fix the situation, but it is a start at repairing trust. (Reinecke, Thilo, Croft & Harmer, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

A comprehensive and systematic search was conducted using the Pubmed, Cochrane Library, Scopus, and Web of Science electronic databases before. This search was based on the following keywords and combinations: (“cognitive behavior* OR cognitive therapy OR behavior therapy OR CBT”) AND (“MRI or magnetic resonance imaging or fMRI or functional magnetic resonance imaging or PET or positron emission tomography or SPECT or single photon emission computed/tomography”). Inclusion criteria required studies to (1) be part of a clinical trial examining cognitive behavioral therapy in Mythomania disorders; (2) compare the neural changes between pre-treatment and post-treatment using fMRI during a task; (3) conduct whole-brain voxel-wise analyses; (4) report results as coordinates in standard Talairach or MNI space; (4) publish in English. Some studies were excluded due to: (1) presenting only baseline coordinates; (2) reporting resting-state fMRI, functional connectivity, voxel-based morphometry, or region-of-interest analyses. If different studies or tasks used the same subjects, we included the study or task which had the largest sample. And Studies that found no significant differences were excluded. The entire search process is shown in the flowchart below.

Cluster size (mm ³)	ALE	MNI-coordinates			Brain region
		X	V	z	
Cognition task					
1,549	0.008694564	0	46	6	Left anterior cingulate
1,066	0.005506158	-18	-12	61	Left middle frontal gyrus
All task					
1,393	0.009742522	-16	-72	12	Left cuneus

Activation Likelihood Estimation Meta-Analysis of Emotion Task Following Cognitive Behavioral Therapy For emotion tasks, we performed the same procedure. No clusters showed significant overlap in ALE maps.

Activation Likelihood Estimation Meta-Analysis of All Tasks Following Cognitive Behavioral Therapy. The ALE meta-analysis was performed on mythomania disorder areas displaying altered

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activation during all tasks from pre to post-CBT with P -value = 0.05, cluster-level = 0.05 and threshold permutations = 1,000. The results revealed that the left cuneus displayed significantly decreased activation.

Result revealed that adolescents seek validation and approval from their peers and authority during adolescence. Lying can be a means to fit in or appear more accomplished than they actually are. By exaggerating their achievements or experiences, they hope to gain social status and acceptance within their peer groups. One of the significant reasons behind adolescent lying is the pressure to fit in and gain acceptance among their peers. Teenagers may feel compelled to lie about their experiences, possessions, or achievements to enhance their social status or avoid feeling left out. With the prevalence of social media platforms, adolescents are constantly exposed to curated versions of other people's lives. This can create a distorted sense of reality, leading them to feel the pressure to present themselves in a way that aligns with the perfect images they see online. In their quest to maintain a desirable online character, they may resort to lying about their experiences or altering their appearance. (Reinecke, Thilo, Croft. & Harmer. 2023).

CONCLUSION

Mythomania is a complex condition that can cause a great deal of harm to relationships. The constant lying, manipulation, and lack of empathy associated with the condition can erode trust and cause emotional pain for both partners. However, with the right treatment and a commitment to change, it is possible to overcome the challenges of mythomania and rebuild a strong and healthy relationship based on honesty and trust. Mythomania is a complex disorder characterized by recurrent and persistent fabrications and untruths. The disorder is associated with a range of comorbidities, including depression, anxiety, and substance abuse. Treatment approaches vary and often include a combination of psychotherapy, pharmacotherapy, and cognitive-behavioral therapy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study recommend that parent should pay attention to changes in behavior in adolescent behavior. Sudden changes in character, such as increased aggression, defensiveness, or withdrawal, could be indicators that something is amiss. Keep an eye out for unexplained mood swings or inconsistencies in their emotional responses.

Body Language: Watch for non-verbal cues that can often reveal a lack of honesty. Notice if your teen avoids eye contact, fidgets excessively, or displays defensive postures, such as crossed arms or crossed legs. These physical indicators may suggest that your teen is withholding the truth.

Communication Patterns: Listen closely to your teen's choice of words and the way they communicate. Look for inconsistencies or contradictions in their stories. Pay attention to excessive use of vague language or an avoidance of providing specific details. Additionally, be aware of any sudden changes in their communication style, such as repeatedly using phrases like "I don't remember" or "I don't know."

It is essential to create an environment of open communication and trust with your teenager. Avoid jumping to conclusions or accusing them without sufficient evidence. Instead, use these observations as starting points for honest conversations and a deeper understanding of their behavior. By maintaining a supportive and non-judgmental approach, you increase the chances of your teen feeling comfortable enough to confide in you truthfully.

With these strategies in mind, parents can develop a keener awareness of their adolescent's behavior and improve their ability to spot potential lies. By maintaining open lines of communication and building a foundation of trust, parents can foster healthy relationships with their teenagers and navigate the challenges of adolescence together. Further research is needed to better understand the development and treatment of this disorder.

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